

1st

INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE (IMSC 2018)
Tetova, Macedonia

THEME:

***Empowering Science and Education through
Research and Emerging Technologies***

IMSC-2018 focuses on the core Scientific Sections, such as:

- Modern Science
- Ancient Science
- Science & Society
- Science & Humanities
- Architecture & Design
- Science & Arts

Conference Speakers

Hyreme Gurra Erik Petersen Filip Duma Mary Peacock Ellie Dawson Arburim Iseni Festim Halili Juan Varela

Conference Sponsors

Venue: Hotel LIRAK
Tetovo - Macedonia

ISBN 978-608-66191-0-7

9 786086 619107

Empowering Science and Education
through Research and Emerging Technologies

Association Institute
of
English Language and American Studies

**BOOK OF
PROCEEDINGS**

1st International Multidisciplinary Scientific Conference
IMSC 2018 – May 26, 2018
Tetova, Macedonia

Editors:

Arburim Iseni
Juan José Varela Tembra
María Mercedes Santiso Pérez